

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Effect of soil acidity on germination of rice

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Ninety germplasms from the 1985 Acid Lowland Soils Screening Set (IRTP) were evaluated for direct seeding in saline acid lowland soils, where high germination is a prerequisite.

Seeds were sown in triplicate, at 20 seeds/dish, in petri dishes containing 60 g of soil (silty clay) having ECe 11.3 dS/m and pH 3.2. After sowing, 40 ml of distilled water was added immediately and 10 ml water at 5d

Germination of rice germplasm in acid soil (pH 3.2, ECe 11.3 dS/m). West Bengal, India.

Varieties and lines with indicated germination percentage			
100-80%	79-10%	69-50%	49-40%
IR13423-17-1-2-1	IR13149-43-2	B2149b-Pn-26-1-1	BW295-4
IR19661-13-3-2	IR13419-113-1	IR13146-45-2	IR13168-143-1
ITA230	IR25588-7-3-1	IR13146-45-2-3	IR32
Khao Tah Haeng 17	IR31917-31-3-2	IR9764-45-2-2	IR42
Mahsuri	IR3839-1		IR4227-109-1-3-3
			IR5
			IR8192-31-2-1-2
6.7	Average height on day 15 (cm)		5.7
	6.7	6.4	

intervals. The dishes were kept at room temperature (30°C) in the laboratory for 15 d. Germination was recorded daily and the average height of seedlings per dish was measured on day 15 (see table).

Of the 90 lines, 45 did not germinate. Five entries had more than 80% germination and another 5 had 70-80%. These 10 lines seem to be promising in acid saline soils. *ℓ*

Field screening of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils, South China

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In the more than 67,000 ha of acid sulfate soil and acid sulfate swamp in China, major factors limiting rice growth are low pH, Fe and Al toxicity,

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of the acid sulfate soil at Duanfen, South China.

Item	Depth (cm)	
	0-15	30-40
pH (H ₂ O)	3.85	3.07
pH (KCl)	3.17	2.65
Total N (%)	0.221	0.170
Organic C (%)	3.13	3.19
Available P (Olsen, ppm)	1.63	1.53
Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	0.290	0.490
Available Zn (ppm)	7.8	8.0
Water soluble SO ₄ (meq/100 g)	0.44	4.59
Active Fe (%)	2.7	2.36
Active Mn (ppm)	20.1	25.1
Particle size (%)		
Sand (0-0.05 mm)	6.6	23.8
Silt (0.05-0.001 mm)	62.9	52.6
Clay (<0.001 mm)	30.4	23.6

Table 2. Iron toxicity tolerance scores and yields of rice with 2 fertilizer treatments on an acid sulfate soil, Duanfen, South China.^a

Variety	Iron toxicity tolerance scores ^b		
	4 WT	8 WT	Grain yield ^c (g/plot)
	<i>40 kg N + 33 kg K/ha</i>		
IR36	3.5 bc	2.0 ab	725 cd
IR50	3.5 bc	2.3 cd	815 bcd
IR58	3.4 ab	2.2 bcd	540 f
IR19058-107-1	3.6 bc	2.3 cd	125 cd
IR29725-22-3-3-3	4.0 d	2.5 d	460 f
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	3.1 cd	2.3 bcd	750 cd
Duansan (local variety)	3.5 bc	2.1 abc	760 cd
Shanyou (hybrid variety)	3.5 bc	2.1 abc	915 ab
Guichao (local variety)	3.1 a	1.9 a	1085 a
	<i>40 kg N + 33 kg K + 17.6 kg P + 3000 kg CaO/ha</i>		
IR36	2.9 a	2.1 ab	150 cdef
IR50	3.1 a	2.3 abc	790 bcd
IR58	2.9 a	2.6 c	757 f
IR19058-107-1	2.9 a	2.3 abc	735 def
IR29725-22-3-3-3	3.4 a	2.4 bc	515 f
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	3.5 a	2.4 bc	700 def
Duansan (local variety)	3.1 a	2.5 c	935 ab
Shanyou (hybrid variety)	3.0 a	2.4 bc	925 abc
Guichao (local variety)	2.9 a	2.0 a	1060 a

^aIn the column in the same treatment, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b1 = normal plant, 9 = nearly dead or dead plant, 3 = tolerant, 6 or more = susceptible. WT = weeks after transplanting. ^cAv of 3 replications.

P deficiency, and excess sulfate. Eighteen rice varieties and lines (15 from the International Rice Testing Program) were screened under 2 fertilizer

treatments, N + K and N + K + P + Ca, in an acid sulfate soil (Table 1) at Duanfen, Taishan county, Guangdong Province, Apr 1985. The amount of

fertilizer was 40 kg N (urea), 17.6 kg P (superphosphate), 33 kg K (potassium chloride), and 3,000 kg CaO (calcium carbonate)/ ha .

Forty-day-old seedlings were planted at 20×20cm spacing in a randomized

complete block design. Plants were scored for Fe toxicity on a 1-9 scale at 4 and 8 wk after transplanting. Grain yield was recorded at maturity.

Varietal differences in tolerance for Fe toxicity were noticed. Fe toxicity was

more severe at 4 wk than at 8 wk after transplanting (Table 2). Addition of P and Ca fertilizers reduced its extent. Local variety Guichao yielded significantly more than any of the test varieties. *ℒ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Experimental mutagenic method for improving rice strains in Vietnam

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The National Strain Testing Centre (NSTC) of Vietnam has tested two rice mutants. Mutant DB250 is the result of irradiating F₁ dry grains from the cross of TB₁ (a Vietnamese local variety) and IR22 at 25 kR along with 0.02% N-Nitrozo N-dimethylurea as spray for 6 h.

DB250 is 1.35-1.50 m high, has a hard and big culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to 120 kg N/ha. It was

submerged 7-10 d after 4 wk of culture, but mortality was not high. At maximum tillering, submergence for 12 d resulted in 20% mortality, compared with 80% for IR27 and several IRRI strains. DB250 has a 1000-grain weight of 26-27 g and yields 4.5 t/ha over a large area. In NST-C tests in 1980-83 in 14 provinces of the North, DB250 was first among 16 adapted submergence-tolerant rices.

Mutant NN22-98 was obtained in 1973 by treating IR22 grains with 0.02% N-NitroLoethylurea for 18 h (pH 7). It was separated from the M₂ population in 1974.

NN22-98 is 1.2-1.4 m high, has a hard culm, is adapted to deep water, and responds to as much as 100 kg N/ha. Its 1,000-grain weight is 29-31 g, compared with the normal 23-25 g. The plant has field resistance to brown planthopper biotypes 1 and 2. Mean yield is 4.4-4.6 t/ha. Grain quality is better than that of IR22.

NN22-98 was third among 16 strains of summer rice tested by the NSTC in 1980-83 in 19 provinces of the North. It is still being tested by the Ministry of Agriculture. *ℒ*

Comparison of rice hybrids and local varieties at TNRRRI

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Seven rice hybrids from IRRI were tested against three short-duration and five medium-duration Tamil Nadu varieties during 1984 kharif. The trial was laid out in a randomized block with three replications. The 24-d-old seedlings were planted, 1 seedling/hill spaced 20 cm between rows and 15 cm within rows, in 10.35 m² plots and fertilized 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. No plant protection measures were taken, as there was no pest or disease incidence during growth.

Among the hybrids studied, Wei You 64 flowered very early (72 d after seeding [DAS]); IR21895-90-3A/IR54 and IR46830A/IR13292-5-2 flowered late (106 DAS). The remaining hybrids

Performance of rice hybrids and local varieties. TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Hybrid and variety	Days to 50% flowering	Height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
Wei You 64	72	89.6	4.5
IR46831A/IR54	87	87.5	4.2
IR41828A/Milyang 54	77	81.9	3.7
IR365A/Milyang 54	87	93.7	3.5
97A/Milyang 54	78	97.3	3.1
IR21895-90-3A/IR54	106	123.3	4.0
IR46830A/IR13292-5-2	106	89.4	4.2
IR50 (IR2153-14-1-6-2/IR28//IR36)	76	85.3	4.1
TKM9 (TKM7/IR8)	77	94.9	4.0
ADT36 (Tiruveni/IR20)	79	94.3	4.0
Co 42 (RP-31-49-2/Lab Muey Mahag)	102	124.0	4.2
IR20 (Peta*3/TN1//TKM6)	103	104.4	3.9
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	99	104.4	4.1
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	99	101.4	4.0
White Ponni (AD)	101	152.8	3.9
CD			3.8
CV			9.5

flowered between 77 and 87 DAS (see table).

IR21895-90-3A/IR54 was tallest of the hybrids, and lodged. White Ponni (AD), one of the medium-duration tall check varieties, also lodged. Check Co

42 partly lodged.

Although yield differences among the hybrids and the check varieties were significant, the yield potential of the hybrids was less than 4.5 t/ha. The maximum yield (4.5 t/ha) was registered